

Anomaly Detection of Aircraft on Final Approach to an Aerodrome with Temporal Fusion Transformers

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Abstract—The growing complexity of modern aviation demands robust anomaly detection methods for flight safety and efficiency. Traditional machine learning methods struggle with scalability, interpretability, and adaptability, while deep learning techniques like autoencoders (AEs) and variational autoencoders (VAEs) learn normal flight patterns but remain sensitive to training anomalies and lack interpretability. This paper introduces a Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT)-based anomaly detection framework, which reformulates anomaly detection as a trajectory prediction task. Unlike AEs and VAEs, TFT integrates static (e.g., airport and runway data) and dynamic variables to enhance context-awareness and generalization across diverse flight operations. TFT leverages prediction errors to effectively identify deviations from normal behavior while maintaining interpretability. Experimental evaluations on flight track data show that TFT outperforms autoencoder-based methods, reducing false positives while preserving high anomaly detection sensitivity. The results highlight TFT’s potential for scalable, interpretable, and data-efficient anomaly detection to improve aviation safety in dynamic operational environments.

Keywords—Anomaly Detection; Artificial Intelligence; Machine Learning; Safety; Transformers; Vulnerability Discovery.

I. INTRODUCTION

Despite the decline in accident rates, a significant proportion of both fatal and non-fatal aviation accidents continue to occur during the approach phase of flight [1]. With the growing demand for air mobility, the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and the aviation industry have emphasized the need for proactive risk management. This involves identifying vulnerabilities and assessing unknown risks (“unknown unknowns”) or accident precursors to mitigate potential hazards before they escalate into incidents.

Current Flight Operational Quality Assurance (FOQA) methodologies primarily focus on predefined operational or safety issues, relying on watch lists and exceedance thresholds. While effective for monitoring known risks, these approaches are inherently limited in detecting emerging risks or anomalies that fall outside predefined parameters. Additionally, traditional methods often struggle to analyze large, high-dimensional datasets, making it difficult to identify subtle patterns or anomalies. As a result, there is a growing need

for innovative, data-driven methods that enable proactive risk identification and mitigation.

Several techniques have been explored for anomaly detection in aviation. For example, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) reduces the dimensionality of data by capturing the directions (principal components) that explain maximum variance. Anomalies are identified as points with high reconstruction errors or those far from the principal subspace [2], [3]. Similarly, kernel-based methods such as One-Class support vector machine (SVM) map data into a higher-dimensional space and learn a boundary around nominal data, flagging points outside the boundary as anomalies [4].

Traditional machine learning (ML), like clustering and density-based methods, have also been widely applied. Techniques like DBSCAN and k -means group nominal trajectories into clusters and identify outliers as anomalies [5]–[7]. Density-based methods, such as Local Outlier Factor (LOF) and Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs), have been employed to model local densities and probability distributions of nominal behaviors [8], [9]. While effective, these methods face several challenges, including sensitivity to hyperparameters (e.g., neighborhood size in DBSCAN, k in LOF), assumptions of uniform density, computational inefficiency for large datasets, and the curse of dimensionality when applied to high-dimensional features, e.g., latitude, longitude, altitude.

To address these limitations, more recent techniques leverage deep learning (DL) architectures. For example, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) have been applied to detect anomalies during approach phases by capturing temporal dependencies [10]–[12]. Autoencoders (AEs) have emerged as the status quo in anomaly detection, learning to reconstruct normal patterns and flagging anomalies based on reconstruction errors [13], [14]. Variants such as Variational Autoencoders (VAEs) and Long short-term memory (LSTM)-based Autoencoders have been used to model nonlinear dependencies and time-series data [15]. However, these methods face key challenges, including sensitivity to anomalies in training data, dependence on well-curated nominal datasets, and lack of interpretability.

In this paper, we propose a novel perspective on anomaly detection by reformulating the problem as a trajectory prediction task. Our approach leverages the Temporal Fusion

Transformer (TFT), a powerful and interpretable model, to predict future trajectory steps of normal flights. Anomalies are detected as predictions with high errors, allowing the model to capture deviations effectively. Unlike traditional methods, the proposed framework can integrate static variables (e.g., airport and runway information) and is inherently interpretable, offering insights into the features contributing to anomalies.

In particular, the key contributions of this work are as follows:

- *Reformulation of Anomaly Detection*: We redefine anomaly detection as a trajectory prediction problem that incorporates all relevant variables, including static ones (e.g., airport and runway information), and provides interpretability.
- *Exploitation of Transformers*: We leverage Transformers, the backbone of modern sequence modeling tasks, for capturing long-range dependencies in flight trajectories.
- *Introduction of Statistical Measures*: We use interquartile range (IQR) as a robust statistical measure to detect anomalies, avoiding the need for arbitrary thresholds.
- *Robustness Analysis*: We conduct extensive evaluations on out-of-distribution (OOD) data to assess model robustness and generalizability.
- *Sensitivity Analysis*: We analyze the impact of training anomalies on model performance.

II. TEMPORAL FUSION TRANSFORMER (TFT) FOR ANOMALY DETECTION

The TFT is a state-of-the-art DL architecture designed for interpretable and accurate multi-horizon time series forecasting [16]. In this work, we reformulate the flight anomaly detection problem as a prediction problem by leveraging the powerful predictive capabilities of the TFT [16]. The remainder of this section is organized as follows: first, we provide an in-depth overview of the TFT model, and then we discuss its adaptation for anomaly detection.

A. The Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) Model

Since its introduction by the Google Cloud AI team, the TFT has been shown to excel in prediction tasks that involve forecasting multiple variables simultaneously over multiple future time steps [16]. The TFT is designed to handle static features (e.g., location-specific attributes such as arrival airport or runway) and temporal features, which in the context of flight track data include time-varying inputs like altitude, airspeed, wind speed, and aircraft sensor values. It can also incorporate known future inputs, such as scheduled flight paths or predicted weather conditions.

TFT excels at multi-horizon forecasting tasks where the objective is to predict multiple variables of interest, \mathbf{y} , for multiple future time steps, $t+1$ to $t+\tau$ with τ is the size of the prediction horizon. The time-varying inputs to the TFT, denoted as \mathcal{X} , are constructed by combining the following:

- **Historical Observations** \mathbf{x} : unknown features that are observed up to a certain time step (t). These features are not known in advance and are only available as part of historical data, i.e., only available from $t-k$, $t-k+1$, ..., t , where k denotes the history window. We will

call these the Observed Inputs and will be denoted as $\mathbf{x}_{t-k}, \mathbf{x}_{t-k+1}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_t$.

- **Target Variables** (\mathbf{y}): measured values of the variables of interest only available from $t-k$, $t-k+1, \dots, t$. We will define these as Past Targets and denote them as $\mathbf{y}_{t-k}, \mathbf{y}_{t-k+1}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_t$.
- **Known Future Inputs** (\mathbf{z}): features that are known in advance, spanning from the history window ($t-k$) to the prediction horizon ($t+\tau$). For simplicity, we will refer to them as Known Inputs and denote them with $\mathbf{z}_{t-k}, \mathbf{z}_{t-k+1}, \dots, \mathbf{z}_t, \mathbf{z}_{t+1}, \dots, \mathbf{z}_{t+\tau}$.

In addition to the temporal inputs \mathcal{X} , the TFT is fed with static covariates \mathcal{S} . The model outputs point predictions, $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t+1}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t+\tau}$, and confidence intervals for the target variables \mathbf{y} . Figure 1 shows illustration of the TFT forecasting procedure applied to a single target variable, e.g., the Airspeed. We use blue for the inputs and orange for the outputs.

The TFT combines the strengths of several advanced components to effectively model complex temporal relationships, handle diverse types of input data, and provide interpretability for its predictions. Specifically, the TFT key features are:

- **Gated Residual Networks (GRNs)**: They allow the model to adaptively determine the importance of input features and simplify the architecture by omitting unused components.
- **Variable Selection Networks**: They dynamically identify the most relevant features, reducing noise and improving interpretability.
- **Static Covariate Encoders**: By separately encoding static inputs (e.g., fixed attributes) and temporal inputs (e.g., time-varying variables), it adapts to both static and dynamic data aspects.
- **Multi-Head Attention Mechanism**: Using interpretable self-attention, TFT captures long-term dependencies across time steps, enabling it to focus on the most relevant portions of the time series.

An illustration of the TFT architecture is proposed in Fig. 2. We report below a detailed description of the key components while for additional details about the TFT, we refer the reader to the original paper [16].

1) *Gated Residual Network (GRN)*: A key component of the TFT is represented by the Gated Residual Network (GRN) which provides the flexibility to apply non-linearity only when needed. Given a primary input a and an optional context input c , the GRN can be defined as follows:

$$\text{GRN}_{\omega}(a, c) = \text{LayerNorm}(a + \text{GLU}_{\omega}(\gamma)), \quad (1)$$

where *LayerNorm* is the standard layer normalization, GLU stands for the Gated Linear Unit, and ω represents weight sharing. The GLU is designed to provide flexible complexity by skipping unused parts of the architecture and adapting to the data complexity. Given an input γ , the GLU is computed as:

$$\text{GLU}_{\omega}(\gamma) = \sigma(W_{1,\omega}\gamma + b_{1,\omega}) \odot (W_{2,\omega}\gamma + b_{2,\omega}), \quad (2)$$

where $W_{(\cdot)}$ and $b_{(\cdot)}$ are the weights and biases for the layer, σ denotes the sigmoid activation function, and \odot represents

Figure 1: An illustration of the TFT forecasting procedure. For simplicity, we show one target variable y : Airspeed. The TFT is fed with Observed Inputs, Known Inputs, Past Targets and Static Covariates to predict multiple time-steps, $t + 1$ to $t + \tau$, for the Airspeed (Target Variable). Point Prediction and Confidence Intervals are available at the output of the model.

the element-wise product. The input γ to the GLU in (1) is computed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma &= W_{3,\omega}\eta + b_{3,\omega}, \\ \eta &= \text{ELU}(W_{4,\omega}a + W_{5,\omega}c + b_{4,\omega}),\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

where $W_{(\cdot)}$ and $b_{(\cdot)}$ are the weights and biases for these two intermediate layers, and ELU stands for Exponential Linear Unit. ELU activation function is defined as:

$$\text{ELU}(x) = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x > 0, \\ \alpha(e^x - 1), & \text{if } x \leq 0, \end{cases}\quad (4)$$

with $\alpha > 0$ a hyperparameter that controls the saturation level for negative inputs x .

2) *Variable Selection Network (VSN)*: VSN is used to automatically filter out less useful static and temporal inputs. This process allows the model to prioritize the features that most significantly contribute to the TFT's predictions. Separate VSNs are defined for static, past, and future inputs, as highlighted in Fig. 2 with different colors. However, the underlying operations performed on these inputs remain essentially the same. Without loss of generality, let us consider past inputs. Before feeding them to the model, transformations are applied using either linear projections or embeddings. Let $\xi_t^{(j)}$ be the transformed input of the j th variable at time t , and Ξ_t be the flattened vector of the combined variables at time t , i.e.,

$$\Xi_t = \left[\xi_t^{(1)\top}, \dots, \xi_t^{(m_x)\top} \right]^\top.$$

First, each $\xi_t^{(j)}$ undergoes a non-linear processing through a dedicated $\text{GRN}_{\xi^{(j)}}$ as in (5).

$$\tilde{\xi}_t^{(j)} = \text{GRN}_{\xi^{(j)}} \left(\xi_t^{(j)} \right).\quad (5)$$

In parallel, Ξ_t and an optional external context \mathbf{c}_s are used to compute the vector of variable selection weights $\mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{X}_t}$ as in

(6). The external context \mathbf{c}_s is not provided for the VSN of the static variables, as it is derived from the static covariate encoder (architecture component that follows the static VSN as shown in Fig. 2).

$$\mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{X}_t} = \text{Softmax}(\text{GRN}_{\mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{X}_t}}(\Xi_t, \mathbf{c}_s)).\quad (6)$$

The processed variables $\tilde{\xi}_t^{(j)}$ and the selection weights $\mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{X}_t}$ are used to compute output of the VSN as:

$$\tilde{\xi}_t = \sum_{j=1}^{m_x} v_{\mathcal{X}_t}^{(j)} \tilde{\xi}_t^{(j)},\quad (7)$$

where $v_{\mathcal{X}_t}^{(j)}$ is the j th component of the vector $\mathbf{v}_{\mathcal{X}_t}$.

3) *Static Covariate Encoder*: The Static Covariate Encoder is a key component of the TFT, helping the model to integrate static attributes into the forecasting process. These static attributes (e.g., location, aircraft characteristics) are critical for making accurate predictions, but remain constant over time. The encoder generates four context vectors ($\mathbf{c}_s, \mathbf{c}_e, \mathbf{c}_c, \mathbf{c}_h$) that summarize these static features and serve distinct purposes within the architecture. These context vectors are used throughout different parts of the TFT architecture, ensuring that the model considers both static and time-dependent inputs simultaneously.

In detail, \mathbf{c}_s is used in the VSN to compute the variable weights as in (6). $\mathbf{c}_e, \mathbf{c}_c$ are used to initialize the cell state and hidden state respectively of the sequence-to-sequence layers (i.e., LSTMs) that locally process known and observed temporal inputs. Additionally, to improve the modeling of time-dependent variables, \mathbf{c}_h is used to enhance the temporal inputs to the first GRNs in the Temporal Fusion Decoder.

4) *Multi-Head Attention Mechanism*: The temporal fusion decoder learns long-term dependencies present within inputs. These dependencies are captured using a masked interpretable multi-head attention block, which allows the model to focus on relevant temporal patterns while maintaining interpretability. Given the query, key and values matrices, Q, K , and V ,

Figure 2: An illustration of the Temporal Fusion Transformer (TFT) architecture. The TFT combines LSTM-based sequence modeling with interpretable attention mechanisms to capture both short- and long-term dependencies in time series data. The architecture consists of several key components, including variable selection networks, LSTM-based encoder-decoder, gated residual networks (GRNs), and a masked multi-head attention mechanism.

supplied as inputs, the classical attention mechanism follows the formula:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = A(Q, K)V \quad (8)$$

where d_k is the dimensionality of the keys and the normalization function $A(\cdot)$ is usually selected as:

$$A(Q, K) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right). \quad (9)$$

To enhance the model's ability to focus on different parts of the input simultaneously, the TFT employs the multi-head attention mechanism:

$$\text{MultiHead}(Q, K, V) = [H_1, \dots, H_{m_H}]W_H, \quad (10)$$

$$H_h = \text{Attention}\left(QW_Q^{(h)}, KW_K^{(h)}, VW_V^{(h)}\right) \quad (11)$$

where $W_Q^{(h)}$, $W_K^{(h)}$, and $W_V^{(h)}$ are weights matrices for queries, keys and values, while W_H combines the heads outputs linearly. However, the classical implementation ((10), (11)) does not allow explicit indication of the importance of specific features, as the weights are not shared across heads. To address this limitation, an improved version, termed *Interpretable Multi-Head Attention*, was introduced with additive aggregation of all heads:

$$\text{InterpretableMultiHead}(Q, K, V) = \tilde{H}W_H \quad (12)$$

$$\tilde{H} = \frac{1}{m_H} \sum_{h=1}^{m_H} \text{Attention}\left(QW_Q^{(h)}, KW_K^{(h)}, VW_V^{(h)}\right), \quad (13)$$

with W_V the value weights shared across all heads. This new formulation allows the user to analyze the set of attention weights, rendering the model more interpretable.

5) *Additional Information*: The temporal fusion decoder (blue box in Fig. 2) includes a series of layers dedicated to capture temporal relationships present in the inputs. The first set of operations (GRNs) are designed to merge temporal features with static metadata. Then, the matrix $\Theta(t)$ of the obtained features is fed to the Multi-Head Attention operation. Note that $Q = K = V = \Theta(t)$ in Eq. (12).

The TFT model is designed to generate prediction intervals in addition to point predictions by simultaneously outputting different percentiles (e.g., 10th, 50th, and 90th) for each time step. TFT is trained using the quantile loss [16].

B. Training and Inference Mechanism for Flight Data

The TFT operates as a supervised forecasting model, learning to predict the next τ time steps based on prior observed data. Being a supervised model, it requires a training phase to learn from labeled data, followed by an inference phase where predictions are generated for unseen data. Below, we describe the training and inference mechanisms.

1) *Training*: During training, all flights in the training dataset are concatenated into a single continuous sequence. After defining a history window (k) and a prediction window (τ), the data is prepared by extracting multiple training samples through a sliding window approach. Specifically, overlapping windows are generated by sliding the window

forward one step at a time. Each window consists of a history segment of k time steps, followed by a target segment of τ time steps, which serves as the prediction ground truth (label).

For example, given a history window of $k = 40$ and a prediction window of $\tau = 20$, the first sample would use time steps 0 to 40 as the history and 41 to 60 as the target. The window then slides forward by one step, creating a new sample with time steps 1 to 41 as the history and 42 to 61 as the target, and so on. This process continues, generating overlapping samples until the entire dataset is processed. This method ensures that the model is exposed to a large number of training samples, improving its ability to learn temporal patterns across the dataset.

To better accommodate our flight data, we introduce a *restart_time* variable, a known input that resets to 0 at the start of each flight and increments to the length of the flight. This variable ensures that the model can effectively learn to transition between flights of different lengths while maintaining temporal consistency.

2) *Inference*: At inference, the TFT is applied independently to each flight. However, because the TFT operates on fixed-length windows, it is applied multiple times to cover the entire length of the flight. While the sliding mechanism is similar to the one used during training, the sliding window during inference is equal to the prediction window (τ), rather than advancing by one time step. As shown in Fig. 3, the inference mechanism divides the flight into overlapping windows, where the history window provides the context for predicting the subsequent prediction window. Assuming the same values as above, the inference proceeds as follows:

- Feed the first window (time steps 0 to 40) into the model to predict the next 20 steps (time steps 41 to 60).
- Shift the window forward by 20 steps and repeat the process. The second window will use time steps 20 to 60 as the history to predict the next 20 steps (time steps 61 to 80).

This process continues until predictions are made for the entire flight. By sliding the window and generating predictions incrementally, the TFT can produce forecasts for flights of arbitrary length, despite operating on fixed-size windows.

C. Anomaly Detection with TFT

To detect anomalies, we leverage the predictions produced by the TFT. It is important to note that anomaly detection is performed in an unsupervised manner, as the model is not provided with labels for anomalous flights. The model predicts target variables $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t+1}, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t+2}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{y}}_T$ for future time steps (T being the last time step in a flight). These predictions are compared against the ground truth target variables $\mathbf{y}_{t+1}, \mathbf{y}_{t+2}, \dots, \mathbf{y}_T$, and the discrepancy is quantified using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) computed separately for each component of the target variable vector \mathbf{y} . Specifically, for each target variable y , we compute:

$$\text{MSE}_j = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{i=1}^{\tau} (\mathbf{y}_{t+i}[j] - \hat{\mathbf{y}}_{t+i}[j])^2 \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, J, \quad (14)$$

where J is the total number of target variables.

For nominal (non-anomalous) data, the TFT is expected to excel at predictions due to its ability to capture temporal patterns effectively, resulting in low MSE values. Higher MSE values, however, may indicate anomalous behavior. Computing the MSE_j for each target variable y individually is critical because different variables may be sensitive to distinct types of anomalies. Averaging the errors across variables could mask important information; for instance, one variable's error may be significantly high, indicating an anomaly, while the others are predicted accurately.

Instead of relying on a fixed threshold for the MSE_j —which can be sensitive to data distribution and outliers—we employ the *Tukey's interquartile range (IQR) rule* to define a robust threshold [17]. This process is applied separately for each MSE_j as follows:

- 1) Compute the MSE_j for each flight in the training dataset after the model has been trained.
- 2) From the distribution of MSE_j values, calculate the first quartile Q_1 and third quartile Q_3 .
- 3) Define the threshold as:

$$\text{Threshold}_j = Q_3 + 1.5 \cdot \text{IQR}, \quad (15)$$

where $\text{IQR} = Q_3 - Q_1$.

Tukey's method ensures that the threshold is independent of outliers in the training dataset. Importantly, it allows anomalies to be included in the training data without requiring manual data cleaning by subject matter experts (SMEs). Even if the training data contains unknown anomalies, the IQR-based threshold remains robust and minimizes their impact. This ensures flexibility and robustness in detecting deviations from nominal behavior, making it suitable for datasets with potential unknown anomalies.

We adopt a conservative approach: a flight is flagged as anomalous if any variable's error exceeds its threshold. This method ensures that all potential anomalies are detected without being masked by averaging effects.

III. DATA

For our analysis, we use two datasets. One is a subset of an open-sourced dataset publicly available at NASA DASHlink Project, another is an in-house dataset provided by the FAA.

A. NASA

This dataset contains de-identified, aggregated flight data recorded over a three-year period from a single type of regional jet in commercial service. These records include detailed information about aircraft dynamics, system performance, and other engineering parameters. Importantly, the dataset does not include any information traceable to specific airlines or manufacturers and is independent of any airline Flight Operational Quality Assurance (FOQA) programs. NASA has provided this data to the public to support research aimed at evaluating and enhancing data mining techniques for promoting aviation safety.

For this study, we utilize the “curated 4-class anomaly detection dataset”, a subset of the larger corpus data. This curated portion consists primarily of 1 Hz recordings from

Figure 3: Illustration of the inference mechanism using a sliding window approach. A history window of size k (e.g., 40) predicts the next τ steps (e.g., 20). The window slides forward by τ until the flight is fully covered.

approximately 99,000 flights on final approach as they cross 1,000 feet before touchdown. Each multidimensional time-series instance includes 160-second window of time capturing 20 measured flight variables. These variables cover a variety of systems, including the state and orientation of the aircraft, control surface positions and inputs, engine parameters, and autopilot modes. In addition to these dynamical variables, the dataset includes metadata such as flight IDs, departure and arrival airports, and runways.

The dataset identifies one nominal class (89,663 flights) and three anomaly types: speed high (7,013 flights), high path (2,207 flights), and late flap setting (954 flights). Labels for the dataset were created using threshold-based rules developed by SMEs. In this study, however, we are not focusing on classifying the specific types of anomalies. Instead, we combine the anomalous classes into a single category, allowing us to analyze and detect anomalies without distinguishing between their specific types.

B. In-House Data

The in-house track data comes from the Airport Surface Detection Equipment Model X (ASDE-X)/Airport Surface Surveillance Capability (ASSC), which integrates data from four sensors: ASR-9, MLAT, SMR, and ADS-B. These sensors generate multiple updates per second; however, the data is downsampled to 1 Hz. For this analysis, data was collected for aircraft flying over the runway threshold, with track points traced back in time up to 2 nautical miles.

The dataset covers a single day and includes landings from all ASDE-X/ASSC sites, with sensitive flights removed. The data includes 17,040 unlabeled flights, meaning the flights are not categorized as anomalous or nominal. It consists of flights landing at 43 different airports, spanning 83 runways, and involving 145 different aircraft types (e.g., 'A124', 'LJ40'). Table I presents the included airports along with their respective flight counts.

Each instance in the dataset is a multidimensional time series with an median length of 48 time steps (mean ≈ 48 , standard deviation ≈ 5). These time series capture 11 dynamic

TABLE I. Airport codes with corresponding flight counts for the in-House data.

ANC 235	ATL 944	BDL 80	BOS 410	BWI 290
CLE 140	CLT 723	CVG 186	DCA 306	DEN 908
DFW 952	DTW 364	EWB 489	FLL 482	HNL 269
HOU 204	IAD 317	IAH 565	JFK 594	LAS 589
LAX 711	LGA 291	MCI 140	MCO 700	MDW 230
MEM 158	MIA 662	MKE 108	MSP 408	MSY 160
ORD 930	PDX 215	PHL 355	PHX 661	PIT 144
PVD 46	SAN 264	SDF 99	SEA 513	SFO 475
SLC 367	SNA 155	STL 201		

flight variables in addition to static information. In particular, the provided features include: aircraft type, arrival airport, arrival runway, time, x, y, z, acceleration, velocity, heading, latitude, longitude, distance to threshold, and glideslope deviation. In addition, we were provided with Flight IDs.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETTINGS

In this study, we compare the performance of the TFT with autoencoders and their variants (e.g., VAE). Since our focus is on the landing phase of the flight, we include metadata such as the arrival airport and arrival runway. For simplicity, we will refer to these as *airport* and *runway* throughout the rest of this paper.

A. Data Preparation

1) *NASA*: For this dataset, we conduct three experiments using different subsets of the data for training and testing. The dataset splits are consistent across all models compared (TFT and AEs) and are detailed in Section IV-B. The target variables selected for this dataset are altitude, airspeed, glideslope deviation, and average core speed.

The TFT model accepts various dynamic and static variables as input. We provide the TFT with all available dynamic data, as well as the airport and runway information. In contrast, for the AE and its variants, the input consists solely of the features that need to be reconstructed, i.e., the selected target variables. All input features are normalized prior to being fed into the models. Specifically, the minimum

and maximum values for each feature are computed from the training dataset and used for normalization during both training and testing.

2) *In-House Data*: Given the unlabeled nature of this dataset, we conducted first an exploratory analysis. First, we sorted flights having unusual behaviors in the z component. Specifically, for each flight, we used the following criteria:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{10} z[i] < \sum_{j=n-9}^n z[j] \implies \text{Flight is unusual} \quad (16)$$

where n is the length of a flight. This process was evaluated by an SME who labeled these flights as go-arounds. The resulting 25 flights were excluded from training and left for the testing phase. Additionally, we randomly selected 15 additional flight for testing. These were checked and labeled by an SME. This test set includes 14 nominal and 1 anomalous flight

For this dataset, we train the TFT model using all available dynamic variables as inputs. The target variables are latitude, longitude, z , and distance to threshold. We select airport, runway and aircraft type as static features.

We normalize only the target variables, while the TFT model handles the remaining input variables internally. Given the variety of airports included in the dataset with varying flight counts (see Table I), we adopt a per-airport normalization approach. Training flights are grouped by airport, and the minimum and maximum values for each target variable are computed within each group. These airport-specific values are subsequently used for normalization during testing.

B. Experimental Design

The comparison is conducted using the NASA data, after which we present the results of TFT applied to in-house track data. For the first two experiments, we focus on comparing the performance of models exclusively trained on nominal data. We focus on showing the generalization and robustness capabilities of the TFT as compared to AEs. For the third experiment, we evaluate the models' sensitivity to anomalies by including anomalous flights in the training corpus. Finally, we test the TFT model on in-house track data. We do not evaluate the AEs as they would require additional data processing given the unequal flight-length characterizing the in-house data.

1) *Single airport/runway experiment*: We filter flights from airport KMSF on Runway 30L from the NASA data. The total number of nominal and anomalous flights is 7189 and 545, respectively. We select randomly 7000 flights for training. The models are tested on the unseen 189 nominal flights and the anomalous flights. To evaluate the robustness of the models, we introduce an out-of-distribution (OOD) validation dataset, consisting of 300 flights randomly selected from three airports (one of which is KMSF).

2) *Multi-airport/runway experiment*: We expand the data to include three airports (KMSF, KDTW, and KMEM) and three runways from each airport. The training dataset consists of 3,000 flights, created by randomly selecting 1,000 flights from each airport. The test set includes 600 flights: 300 unseen nominal flights and 300 anomalous flights. Additionally,

an OOD dataset is constructed by selecting 100 flights from a completely different fourth airport, KOKC, which is not included in the training data.

3) *Sensitivity Experiment*: In this experiment, we build upon the data used in the previous two experiments but introduce anomalous flights into the training datasets. Specifically, we train several AE and TFT models on modified training datasets, where a percentage of nominal flights is replaced with anomalous flights. For example, starting with the 3,000 flights used in the Multi-airport/runway experiment, we replace 1% (30 flights), 5% (150 flights), and so on with anomalous flights.

After training the models on these modified datasets, we evaluate them on unseen nominal and anomalous flights. Due to the relatively small number of anomalies in the Single airport/runway experiment (only 545 anomalous flights), we supplement this dataset with anomalous flights from the same airport but different runways. For simplicity, we use 100 anomalous flights per anomaly type, when available.

4) *In-House data testing*: We train the TFT on the unlabeled 17,000 flights and use the remaining 40 flights for the test phase.

C. Models' Specifications

For this study, we consider a shallow AE, a deep AE, and deep VAEs, and compare with the proposed TFT.

1) *Shallow and Deep AE*: AEs are widely used in anomaly detection due to their ability to learn compact representations of nominal data, with anomalies detected based on reconstruction errors, e.g., MSE. AEs are made of an encoder and a decoder. The encoder takes the input sequence, encodes it into the latent space, and reconstructs it using the decoder. The reconstruction objective minimizes the difference between the input sequence and its reconstruction, enabling the autoencoder to learn a compact representation of the time series.

The shallow AE is composed of an encoder with one LSTM layer and one fully connected (FC) layer projecting to a latent space. The decoder consists of two LSTM layers followed by a FC layer for reconstructing the input time series. For the deep AE, the encoder consists of two bidirectional LSTM layers. A bidirectional LSTM processes the sequence in both forward and backward directions, effectively operating as two LSTMs running in parallel for each layer. The encoded representation is then passed through two FC layers. The decoder consists of four LSTM layers and one FC layer. The first two LSTM layers are unidirectional, while the second stack of two LSTM layers is bidirectional.

We set the hidden dimension size to 128, while the latent dimension is of size 64. The models are trained for 50 epochs using MSE as loss function.

2) *Deep VAE*: VAEs extend AE by imposing a probabilistic latent space, making them a popular choice for modeling variability in the data. We construct a deep VAE with the same architecture as the deep AE, but we only use one FC layer in the encoder. Unlike the standard AE, the deep VAE introduces a probabilistic latent space by learning a mean and variance for the latent representation.

The deep VAE is trained using a combination of MSE as the reconstruction loss and the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence, which regularizes the latent space by encouraging it to follow a standard normal distribution. To analyze the impact of the KL term, we perform a tuning analysis by varying the parameter β , which scales the contribution of the KL term in the total loss. This allows us to control the trade-off between reconstruction accuracy and latent space regularization.

We obtained the best performance by setting $\beta = 1$ for the single airport/runway dataset and $\beta = 10$ for the multiple airports/runways one.

3) *TFT*: The TFT model is built using the architecture in Fig. 2. We use one LSTM layer. The size of all hidden layers is set to 100, while the size of attention heads is 4. The dropout probability is $p = 0.1$. For the NASA data, we select a history window $k = 40$ and a prediction window $\tau = 20$. For the in-house data, the values of the history and prediction windows are 20, and 10, respectively. For both datasets, we train the models for 50 epochs with early stopping. The 50th quantile (i.e., the median) is used as the point estimate prediction. Although the TFT provides confidence intervals, they are not utilized in our analysis.

D. Evaluation Metrics

We evaluate the ability of different models to detect anomalies using the approach described in Section II-C. A flight is flagged as anomalous if at least one variable’s error exceeds the threshold determined by the IQR rule. For the AE and its variants, the reconstruction error (MSE) in (14) is computed as the difference between the reconstructed sequence and the ground truth for all points.

We will report false positives (FP; nominal flights detected as anomalies), false negatives (FN; missed anomalies), and the F1-score as an overall measure of detection performance.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

We report a performance comparison of shallow AE, deep AE, deep VAE and TFT for both the single airport/runway and multiple airports/runways experiments in Tables II, and III, respectively. In both tables, we report FP, FP_{OOD} , which refers to the FP rate for the OOD dataset, FN, and F1-score. The arrows \downarrow and \uparrow indicate whether lower or higher values are preferable, respectively. In Fig. 4, we present the sensitivity analysis conducted for the deep AE, the deep VAE, and the TFT. The plots show the performance of models trained on the data of the single airport/runway experiment. We show the true positive (TP, solid lines) and false positive (FP, dashed lines) rates as a function of the percentage of anomalous data included in the training set.

For the in-house data, the TFT’s FP and FN rates were 7% and 0%, respectively. The TFT successfully detected all anomalies including the go-around flights and the another type of anomaly. To further illustrate model performance, Fig. 5 presents representative examples, including the ASAIC replay screenshots. The TFT predictions are shown in orange, while the ground truth observations are in blue. The figure includes: (a) a nominal validation flight (unseen during training), (b) an

TABLE II. Comparison for Single airport/runway experiment for the NASA data

Architecture	FP (%) \downarrow	FP_{OOD} (%) \downarrow	FN (%) \downarrow	F1-score (%) \uparrow
Shallow AE	19	73	16	83
Deep AE	21	76	15	83
Deep VAE	17	80	19	82
TFT	7	22	18	87

TABLE III. Comparison for Multiple airports/runways experiment for the NASA data

Architecture	FP (%) \downarrow	FP_{OOD} (%) \downarrow	FN (%) \downarrow	F1-score (%) \uparrow
Shallow AE	18	98	18	82
Deep AE	16	100	18	83
Deep VAE	10	100	23	82
TFT	16	15	13	86

anomalous flight, and (c) a go-around example. Notice that the model predictions are very accurate for the nominal scenario (a). On the other hand, the error between the predictions and the ground truth data is higher than for anomalous cases (b) and (c).

B. Discussion

1) *Results Evaluation*: The results demonstrate that the TFT’s ability to incorporate both dynamic and static variables makes it well-suited for complex aviation anomaly detection scenarios. In terms of detected anomalies, we can notice that the deep AE performs slightly better in the single airport/runway experiment (Table II), but the TFT achieves a better performance in the multiple airport/runway scenario (Table III). In general, the TFT achieves a more optimal balance between FN and FP (highest F1-scores in both experiments).

TFT generalizes better to unseen operational environments, as reflected in its significantly lower FP_{OOD} rates. We hypothesize that the robustness of the TFT to OOD is linked to its ability to incorporate static variables. In contrast, the AEs and their variants struggle to generalize, often detecting nearly everything as an anomaly when tested on OOD nominal flights. This highlights that while AEs are suited for anomaly detection, they do not generalize well to other runways or airports. This translates to AEs not being operationally scalable. One may need multiple models - one for each airport/runway, making its scalability very impracticable.

Another key advantage of the TFT is its robustness to anomalies in the training data, as demonstrated in the sensitivity analysis (Fig. 4,). Unlike the AE, whose performance degrades significantly when anomalies are included in the training set, the TFT maintains consistent performance even when up to 10% of the training data contains anomalies. Specifically, a TFT trained with only nominal data, i.e., 0% anomalies in training, performs approximately the same as a TFT model trained with 10% anomalous data included in the training set. Performance begins to degrade slightly when a higher percentage of anomalies is included in training.

This is due to the way the detection threshold is derived from the training distribution of MSEs. When many anomalies

Figure 4: Sensitivity Analysis for the deep AEs (blue), the deep VAEs (red), and the TFTs (black). We report FP (solid lines) and the FN (dashed lines) rates for various models trained by introducing anomalies in the training data of the single airport/runway experiment. We show the different percentages of anomalies on the x -axis.

are present during training, the TFT does not fit to them, this is desirable behavior, but it causes the threshold to rise. As a result, some borderline anomalies at test time may fall below the threshold and go undetected, increasing the FN rate. In contrast, the FN rate for AEs decreases slightly under the same conditions, likely because AEs tend to flag any input that deviates from the training distribution. This includes operationally normal but off-distribution data, which is also reflected in their high FP_{OOD} rates (Table II).

This robustness is critical in aviation applications, where sorting and cleaning training data can be prohibitively time-consuming, and unknown unknowns may be missed. For example, for the in-house dataset, we only sorted the data to obtain labeled test flights to validate the performance of the TFT. Upon further analysis, we concluded that anomalies remained in the training corpus. However, this did not affect the TFT’s ability to detect anomalies at test-time. This indicates that the model can be trained on unlabeled flights and still be effectively deployed.

2) *Interpretability*: The TFT allows us to evaluate and study the importance of each input variable in the prediction process. This is achieved by analyzing the variable selection weights $v_{\mathcal{X}_i}$ (6). For example, we present two sample bar charts depicting the variable importance (%) of each dynamic variable for a sample flight of (Fig. 6) the NASA data and (Fig. 7) the in-house data. We observe that the TFT identifies a subset of key inputs that intuitively play a significant role in predictions. While current deep learning methods often struggle to provide interpretability of results, the TFT offers an appealing alternative with its ability to provide insights into the predictive process.

3) *Computational Complexity*: We report in Table V the parameter counts and their storage requirements for the models trained on the single airport/runway experiment. The parameter count provides a direct indicator of computational complexity. The Shallow AE is the most memory-efficient, while the TFT has the highest memory demand, which comes at the expense of computational efficiency. The VAE introduces an additional overhead for sampling during the

TABLE IV. Inference Times of Different Models

Model	Shallow AE	Deep AE	Deep VAE	TFT
Time (ms)	0.61	0.82	1.25	189.48

TABLE V. Model Parameters and Storage Requirements

	Shallow AE	Deep AE	Deep VAE	TFT
Parameters	308,804	1,465,540	1,457,284	2,040,352
Storage (MB)	1.18	5.59	5.56	7.78

forward pass, but it does not have extra parameters like the Deep AE, which includes an additional fully connected (FC) layer in the encoder.

We also report the inference times for all models for the same experiment, referring to running inference on a single flight (Table IV). All simulations were run on an NVIDIA RTX A6000 GPU. Notice that inference time for the TFT is the highest due to our inference mechanism (II-B2). Before obtaining a complete prediction, the TFT model is applied iteratively to generate forecasts for each prediction window. Despite this, the TFT’s inference time is approximately 0.2 seconds, making it suitable for real-time predictions.

The TFT is computationally the most expensive but provides superior performance, as shown in our results. We note that our implementation uses the TFT from the PyTorch Forecasting library, which includes additional computations during inference—such as generating quantiles for prediction intervals, storing variable importance weights, and computing temporal attention scores for interpretability. These features, while useful for analysis, are not necessary for real-time inference. Therefore, the inference cost can be significantly reduced by customizing the implementation to remove unused components and streamline the prediction pipeline. Future deployment-oriented work can optimize this further, reducing the computational footprint without affecting prediction quality.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a novel approach to aviation anomaly detection by leveraging the capabilities of the TFT model. Our results demonstrated that TFT achieves the best balance between FP and false negatives FN, consistently yielding the highest F1 scores across experiments. Notably, in the in-house dataset, the model successfully detected all anomalies, including all go-around flights. Additionally, the TFT framework scales effectively across different airports and runways, which directly addresses a key limitation of traditional anomaly detection methods. Our findings demonstrate the robustness and scalability of the framework, as well as its ability to handle multimodal and static data effectively.

Beyond its strong detection performance, the TFT provides interpretability by highlighting the importance of input variables in predictions. This feature can potentially facilitate the identification of critical factors contributing to anomalies.

Future work will focus on classifying the type of anomalies detected, moving beyond simple anomaly identification to provide a more granular understanding of flight deviations, such as go-arounds, unstable approaches, altitude deviations, or holding patterns.

Figure 5: Representative TFT model predictions for test flights from the In-House Dataset. We show the TFT predictions (orange) and ground truth (blue) for the four target variables and the ASAIC replay screenshot. Figure (a) depicts a flight identified as nominal, while (b) shows a go-around flight, and (c) presents another anomalous flight.

Figure 6: Variables importance for a sample flight from the NASA data.

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Figure 7: Variables Importance for a sample flight from the In-House data.

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